

Structure of Heptazoline

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The details of the structure of heptazoline, a carbazole alkaloid from *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. have been reported.

IN connection with our studies on carbazole alkaloids, we undertook the examination of *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn., which is taxonomically related to the genera *Glycosmis* and *Murraya* (Fam.: Rutaceae, sub. Fam.: Aurantoidae, Subtribe, Clausenae). The isolation and the preliminary report on the structure of heptazoline appeared in a previous communication¹. Recent synthesis of heptazoline by Kapil *et al.*² prompted us to report the details of the structural studies of heptazoline.

Heptazoline, C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ (1), M⁺ 295, m.p. 212-14°, is an optically inactive homogeneous phenolic compound. It gave a 2,4-DNPH derivative, m.p. 280-81°. It reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate solution, showing the presence of an aldehyde function in it. The ir spectrum of heptazoline, $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3450, 3150, 1623, 1580 and 1500 cm⁻¹, shows the presence of NH, OH, chelated aldehyde and aromatic groups. The uv spectrum, $\lambda_{\max}$ (ethanol) 240, 275 and 298 nm (log ϵ 4.58, 4.6 and 4.40), shows the presence of a 3-formyl carbazole chromophore³ in it. The mass spectrum shows molecular ion peak at *m/z* 295. The pmr spectrum of 1 shows that it has two phenolic hydroxyls (δ 9.82, 11.51) which disappeared on deuteration, one-NH proton (δ 11.25, disappearing on deuteration), and one aldehydic proton (δ 9.9). The three proton singlets at δ 1.65 and 1.81 and doublets for two methylenic protons at 3.63 for (*J* 10 cps) together with the vinylic proton multiplets for one proton at 5.3 show the presence of a dimethyl allyl residue substituted on the carbazole nucleus. The signal of the proton at C-4 of the carbazole nucleus is deshielded (δ 8.28) due to proximity of the formyl group at 3-position and appears as a singlet due to substitution at 2-position.

On zinc dust distillation 1 furnished carbazole (2),⁴ confirming the carbazole skeleton of heptazoline. On treatment with polyphosphoric acid, heptazoline furnished cycloheptazoline, C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ (3), m.p. 290° d, M⁺ 295. In the pmr spectrum of 3 the signals for the γ,γ -dimethylallyl residue was replaced by two symmetrical triplets for 2 protons each at δ 3.13 and 1.98 and a singlet for 6 protons at 1.45. These data account for the 2,2-dimethylpyran ring in cycloheptazoline. The shift of the aldehydic band of 3 from 1630 to 1645 cm⁻¹ in its ir spectrum points out that the hydroxyl

group of 1 chelated to the aldehyde function is involved in cyclisation, which is supported by the absence of the appropriate pmr signal in 3 corresponding to the hydroxyl group at δ 9.82 in 1. The uv spectrum of the monoacetate of cycloheptazoline 4, $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 237, 275 and 295 nm (log ϵ 4.47, 4.60 and 4.54), is very similar to that of dihydromurrayacine⁵ (5) showing that cycloheptazoline has substitution pattern in ring C like 5.

All these data, lent to partial formulation of 1 as 2-hydroxy-1-(γ,γ)dimethylallylcarbazole with an additional hydroxyl group in ring A.

The pmr signal for the second hydroxyl in ring A appeared at δ 11.05 (highly chelated) in 3 and 11.5 in 1. Comparison of the pmr signals of this hydroxyl proton with those of 6-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole (6) and 1-hydroxycarbazole (7) showed it to be closer to that of 1-hydroxycarbazole synthesised in our laboratory by a separate route other than mentioned⁶ previously. Benzene diazonium chloride (8) was reacted with formyl cyclohexanone (9) under Japp-Kilingemann condition when hydrazone (10), m.p. 180°, was obtained, which on indolisation gave 1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole (11), m.p. 169°, M⁺ 185. The oxo-compound (11) on dehydrogenation furnished 1-hydroxycarbazole (7) m.p. 164° (lit⁶. 164°). From all these data, the structure of heptazoline was proposed as 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The samples were dried *in vacuo* over P₂O₅ at 110° for analysis.

Isolation of heptazoline (1): Air dried stem bark of *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. (1 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). On allowing this solution to stand, yellow crystals of heptazoline deposited. This on recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) furnished needle shaped crystals of heptazoline, m.p. 212-14° (Found: C, 73.50; H, 6.09; N, 4.90. C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ calcd. C, 73.20; H, 5.80; N, 4.70%).

2,4-DNPH of heptazoline: 1 on reaction with 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine gave a red precipitate which on recrystallisation from methanol gave dark

(i) PPA, (ii) Zn-dust distillation, (iii) J. K. reaction, (iv) indolisation, (v) Pd/O.

red crystals, m.p. 280-81° (Found : N, 1.4. C₂₅H₂₂-N₂O₂ calcd. N, 7.22%).

Zinc dust distillation of heptazoline : 1 (250 mg) was intimately mixed with zinc dust (100 g) and distilled in a bent hard glass test tube closed at one end with a long neck at the open end. The mass deposited at the cooler part, was taken up in benzene and chromatographed over alumina (5 g). The fraction eluted with benzene after work up furnished crystalline material which after crystallisation furnished a compound, m.p. 225-227°, and showed no depression when mixed with a pure specimen of carbazole. The identity was further established by its superimposable uv spectrum with carbazole, λ_{max} (EtOH) 233, 257, 293, 322 and 336 (log ϵ 4.5, 4.18, 4.10, 3.4 and 3.40).

Cycloheptazoline (3) : 1 was dissolved in ethanol and polyphosphoric acid was added to it. The

mixture was refluxed for 6 h and then worked up. The crude reaction product after crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether furnished a solid, m.p. 270-75°, which on recrystallisation from benzene and petroleum ether gave a crystalline compound, m.p. 290° d (Found : C, 72.9 ; H, 5.55 ; N, 4.58. C₁₈H₁₇NO₂ calcd. C, 73.20 ; H, 5.80 ; N, 4.74%).

Cycloheptazoline monoacetate (4) : 3 (30 mg) in pyridine was treated with acetic anhydride. On pouring the solution in ice-cold water (25 ml) a solid separated which was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 290° d (Found : C, 74.75 ; H, 5.62 ; N, 4.1. C₂₀H₁₈NO₂ calcd. C, 74.75 ; H, 5.96 ; N, 4.36%).

1-Hydroxycarbazole (7) : 2-Formylcyclohexanone (0.15 ml) when reacted with benzene diazonium chloride in presence of sodium acetate (2 g) by slow addition gave the hydrazone, m.p. 180°. The hydrazone was indolised with a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated HCl (4 : 1) for a period of 4 min. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water when a solid separated. The oxo-tetrahydrocarbazole, was purified by chromatography over alumina when light crystalline solid 2, m.p. 169°, was obtained. The ketotetrahydrocarbazole (330 mg) in *p*-cymene was dehydrogenated with Pd/C (5%) throughout a period of 16 h. On working up of the reaction mixture a crystalline compound was obtained, which was recrystallised, m.p. 164° (lit⁶. 164°) (Found : C, 78.51 ; H, 5.23 ; N, 7.4. C₁₂H₉NO calcd. C, 78.67, H, 4.95 ; N, 7.65%).

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